

Figure 26: Relative abundance of proteolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 4. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

For the proteolytic bacterial groups chosen for this analysis only Gammaproteobacteria showed a high abundance for both sexes.

Comparison 5: Young vs Aged mice

For this part of the study, we had a total of 90 young and old (aged) mice with 46 female mice and 44 male mice. We compared the influence of age, sex and CKD on the microbiota. We filtered out the specific samples from the rarefied OTU table to continue with this analysis.

Cage ID	Sex	Age	Treatment	# of mice
251254	F	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
331588	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331589	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331590	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331591	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	1

331592	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331593	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331594	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
332103	F	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	4
332107	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332112	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332115	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332116	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
338900	F	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	4
341560	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	1
341599	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	2
345891	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
345893	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
345894	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
348597	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
348598	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
348601	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
351877	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
351878	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
351879	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
352022	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
354613	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	1
356507	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
388218	F	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	5
388219	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	5

Alpha Diversity

- Alpha diversity is the mean species diversity within samples

Shannon Diversity Index

Figure 27: Shannon diversity by sex and colored by treatment.

Shannon diversity in the aged mice look similar across treatments and sex. For the young mice the male CKD mice have a lower Shannon diversity then the control male samples as well as the young female samples.

Alpha Diversity Statistics

We tested the significance of treatment, sex and age on Shannon diversity with a linear mixed effect model fit by REML.

Random effect: Cage ID
Fixed effects: Shannon ~ treatment1 * sex * age

The linear mixed effect model showed a significant difference of Shannon diversity in the interaction of sex with age ($p=0.0139$).

Richness

The number of species within sample.

Figure 28: Bacterial Richness by sex and colored by treatment group.

Richness is higher in the control mice than in the CKD mice. In particular the young male CKD mice have the lowest richness.

Random effects: CageID
Fixed effects: Observed ~ treatment1 * sex * age

Richness was significantly affected by the interaction of sex with age.

Taxa Bar Plot

Figure 29: Taxa bar plot of aged vs young mice male by sex and CKD status.

Beta Diversity

- The difference in diversity of species between two or more samples, expressed as the total number of species that are unique to each of the ecosystems being compared.

We used the rarefied OTU table that was filtered for the samples in comparison 5 (aged and young both male and female CKD mice) to create a dissimilarity matrix using Bray Curtis. Subsequently we used the Bray Curtis distance matrix to follow up with a PERMANOVA in the Primer+ software.

PERMANOVA

Together with a table of the covariable (cageID) the distance matrix was imported into Primer 6 and a sums of square type I PERMANOVA was run accounting for the covariable: cageID

Accounting for cage treatment (CKD-adenine), sex, age and the interaction between both treatment with age or sex and the interaction of treatment with age and were significant for microbial composition.

PERMANOVA table of results						
Source	df	SS	MS	Pseudo-F	P(perm)	Unique perms
cage_id	1	0.8999	0.8999	4.8191	0.001	997
sex	1	0.96968	0.96968	5.1928	0.001	998
age	1	7.1371	7.1371	38.22	0.001	997
treatment1	1	0.77046	0.77046	4.1259	0.001	999
treatment1xsex	1	0.62692	0.62692	3.3573	0.001	998
treatment1xage	1	0.67328	0.67328	3.6055	0.001	998
sexage	1	1.0171	1.0171	5.4465	0.001	997
treatment1xsexage	1	0.87039	0.87039	4.6611	0.001	996
Res	81	15.126	0.18674			
Total	89	28.09				

NMDS – Beta Diversity plots

Figure 30: NMDS of CKD female mice aged versus young in comparison 5. Colored by treatments, shape for sex and age. Ellipses are colored by treatment, female have solid lines, males have dashed lines. Ellipses are shown at 95% confidence interval.

In the NMDS we can see a clear separation of communities by age (open vs closed shapes) and by sex (shape) as well by treatment (color).

Variance explained

Factor	Variance explained (%)
Cage ID	1.47
Treatment1	2.73
Treatment1*sex	4.04
Treatment1* age	4.49
sex	3.9
age	29.17
Sex * age	6.98
Treatment1* sex *age	12.6
Residual	34.61

Treatment1 explains about 3% of the variance cage explains 1.4%, sex explains ~4%, age ~30% the interaction of sex and age explains ~7% and together with treatment this value increases to ~12%.

Proteolytic and Saccharolytic Bacterial group comparison by treatment

Figure 31: Relative abundance of saccharolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 5. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

From the saccharolytic bacterial groups *Corynebacteriaceae* and *Prevotellaceae* showed very low abundance for treatment and age groups for both sexes. *Lachnospiraceae* showed very high abundance in treatment and age groups for both sexes in comparison to the remaining saccharolytic bacterial groups. The *Erysipelotrichales* show a higher relative abundance aged mice in comparison to the young mice.

Figure 32: Relative abundance of proteolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 5. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

For the proteolytic bacterial groups chosen for this analysis only Gammaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance for both sexes and age groups. Alphaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance only in the aged mice in comparison to all other proteolytic bacterial groups.

Comparison 6: Young vs Aged male mice

For this part of the study, we had a total of 22 young and 22 old (aged) male mice. (44 total). We compared the influence of age and CKD on the microbiota. We filtered out the specific samples from the rarefied OTU table to continue with this analysis.

Cage ID	Sex	Age	Treatment	# of mice
351877	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
351878	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2

351879	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
352022	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
356507	M	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
341560	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	1
341599	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	2
388219	M	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	5
345893	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
345894	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
348597	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
348598	M	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
345891	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
348601	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
354613	M	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	1

Alpha Diversity

- Alpha diversity is the mean species diversity within samples

Shannon Diversity Index

Figure 33: Shannon diversity by age and colored by treatment.

Shannon diversity in the aged mice looks similar between CKD and control mice. For the young mice the diversity is lower for CKD mice in comparison to the young control mice.

Alpha Diversity Statistics

Random effect: Cage ID

Fixed effects: Shannon ~ treatment1 *age

The linear mixed effect model showed a significant difference of Shannon diversity due to age (p=0.0331).

Richness

The number of species within sample.

Figure 34: Bacterial Richness by age and colored by treatment group.

Richness is lower in the young male CKD mice versus all other treatments.

Random effects: CageID

Fixed effects: Observed ~ treatment1 * age

Richness was significantly affected by age ($p=0.0073$).

Taxa Bar Plot

Figure 35: Taxa bar plot of aged vs young mice male by CKD status.

Beta Diversity

- The difference in diversity of species between two or more samples, expressed as the total number of species that are unique to each of the ecosystems being compared.

We used the rarefied OTU table that was filtered for the samples in comparison 6 (aged and young male CKD mice) to create a dissimilarity

matrix using Bray Curtis. Subsequently we used the Bray Curtis distance matrix to follow up with a PERMANOVA in the Primer+ software.

PERMANOVA

Together with a table of the covariable (cageID) the distance matrix was imported into Primer 6 and a sums of square type I PERMANOVA was run accounting for the covariable: cageID

PERMANOVA table of results						
Source	df	SS	MS	Pseudo-F	P(perm)	Unique perms
cage_id	1	1.4634	1.4634	7.6307	0.001	998
age	1	3.564	3.564	18.584	0.001	997
treatment1	1	0.96115	0.96115	5.0117	0.001	998
agextreatment1	1	0.88992	0.88992	4.6403	0.001	998
Res	39	7.4794	0.19178			
Total	43	14.358				

Accounting for cage treatment (CKD-adenine), age and the interaction between treatment with age were significant for microbial composition.

Variance explained

Factor	Variance explained (%)
Cage ID	5.33
Treatment1	8.61
Treatment1* age	15.28

age	35.43
Residual	35.35

Treatment1 explains about 9% of the variance cage explains 5%, age ~35% the interaction of treatment and age explains ~15%. 35% remain unexplained.

NMDS – Beta Diversity plots

Figure 36: NMDS of CKD male mice aged versus young. Colored by treatments, shape for age.

Proteolytic and Saccharolytic Bacterial group comparison by treatment

Figure 37: Relative abundance of saccharolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 6. Boxplots are colored by treatment

From the saccharolytic bacterial groups *Corynebacteriaceae* and *Prevotellaceae* showed very low abundance for treatment and age groups. *Lachnospiraceae* showed very high abundance in treatment and age groups in comparison to the remaining saccharolytic bacterial groups. *Rikenellaceae* show differential abundance in aged mice: the CKD aged male mice have a relative high abundance while the aged control mice show a very low abundance of this bacterial group. The *Erysipelotrichales* show a higher relative abundance aged mice in comparison to the young mice.

Figure 38: Relative abundance of proteolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 6. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

For the proteolytic bacterial groups chosen for this analysis only Gammaproteobacteria and alphaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance for the age groups. Alphaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance only in the aged mice in comparison to all other proteolytic bacterial groups. Gammaproteobacteria are in higher relative abundance in the aged control male mice in comparison to the aged CKD mice. For the young mice the CKD mice have higher relative abundance in Gammaproteobacteria than the control mice.

Comparison 7: Young vs Aged female mice

For this part of the study, we had a total of 24 young and 22 old (aged) female mice. (46 total). We compared the influence of age and CKD on the microbiota. We filtered out the specific samples from the rarefied OTU table to continue with this analysis.

Cage ID	Sex	Age	Treatment	# of mice
331588	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331589	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2

331590	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331591	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	1
331592	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331593	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	2
331594	F	Aged	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	3
251254	F	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	3
388218	F	Aged	Control-not applicable-not applicable	5
332107	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332112	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332115	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332116	F	Young	CKD adenine-not applicable-not applicable	4
332103	F	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	4
338900	F	Young	Control-not applicable-not applicable	4

Alpha Diversity

- Alpha diversity is the mean species diversity within samples

Shannon Diversity Index

Figure 39: Shannon diversity by age and colored by treatment.

Shannon diversity in the aged female mice looks similar between CKD and control mice. We tested the effect of age and treatment with a linear mixed effects model fit by REML.

Alpha Diversity Statistics

Random effect: Cage ID

Fixed effects: Shannon ~ treatment1 *age

The linear mixed effect model showed a no significant difference of Shannon diversity due to age.

Richness

The number of species within sample.

Figure 40: Bacterial Richness by age and colored by treatment group.

Overall richness is slightly lower in the CKD mice the control mice in both age groups.

Random effects: CageID

Fixed effects: Observed ~ treatment1 * age

Richness was not significantly affected by age.

Taxa Bar Plot

Figure 41: Taxa bar plot of aged vs young mice male by CKD status.

Beta Diversity

- The difference in diversity of species between two or more samples, expressed as the total number of species that are unique to each of the ecosystems being compared.

We used the rarefied OTU table that was filtered for the samples in comparison 7 (aged and young female CKD mice) to create a dissimilarity matrix using Bray Curtis. Subsequently we used the Bray Curtis distance matrix to follow up with a PERMANOVA in the Primer+ software.

PERMANOVA

Together with a table of the covariable (cageID) the distance matrix was imported into Primer 6 and a sums of square type I PERMANOVA was run accounting for the covariable: cageID

PERMANOVA table of results						
Source	df	SS	MS	Pseudo-F	P(perm)	Unique perms
cage_id	1	0.66669	0.66669	3.7468	0.001	995
age	1	3.8304	3.8304	21.527	0.001	999
treatment1	1	0.40922	0.40922	2.2998	0.002	997
agextreatment1	1	0.59034	0.59034	3.3177	0.001	998
Res	41	7.2953	0.17794			
Total	45	12.792				

Accounting for cage, treatment (CKD-adenine), age and the interaction between treatment with age were significant for microbial composition.

NMDS – Beta Diversity plots

Figure 42: NMDS of CKD male mice aged versus young. Colored by treatments, shape for age. Ellipses at 95% confidence interval are colored by treatment.

Variance explained

Factor	Variance explained (%)
Cage ID	2.67
Treatment1	2.8
Treatment1* age	9.94
age	39.94
Residual	44.66

Treatment1 explains almost 3% of the variance cage explains 3%, age ~40% the interaction of treatment and age explains ~10%. About 45% of the variance remain unexplained.

Proteolytic and Saccharolytic Bacterial group comparison by treatment

Figure 43: Relative abundance of saccharolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 7. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

From the saccharolytic bacterial groups *Corynebacteriaceae* and *Prevotellaceae* showed very low abundance for treatment and age groups. *Lachnospiraceae* showed very high abundance in treatment and age groups in comparison to the remaining saccharolytic bacterial groups. *Rikenellaceae* show higher abundance in young mice: the CKD young female mice have a relative high abundance while the young control mice show a lower abundance of this bacterial group. The *Erysipelotrichales* show a higher relative abundance in aged female mice in comparison to the young mice.

Figure 44: Relative abundance of proteolytic bacteria by treatment in comparison 7. Boxplots are colored by treatment.

For the proteolytic bacterial groups chosen for this analysis only Gammaproteobacteria and alphaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance for the age groups. Alphaproteobacteria showed a high relative abundance only in the aged mice in

comparison to the other treatment groups. For the young mice the CKD mice have higher relative abundance in Gammaproteobacteria than the control mice.

Methods:

Demultiplexed sequences were imported into the high-performance computing cluster (hpc3) from the Zymo Research server. The forward read sequences were imported into qiime2 using a manifest file. In qiime2 sequences were dereplicated and quality checked as well chimera were removed using DADA2. The operational taxonomical units at 100% similarity (amplicon sequence variants: ASV) were picked with UCLUST within qiime2. The resulting OTU table was rarefied via randomized sampling of sequences without replacement over 100 iterations at a depth of 7562 sequences per sample using the “EcolUtils” package in R version 4.1 (R Core Team, 2018; Salazar, 2020). For the taxonomic identification we trained a classifier using the specific 16S primers (V3-V4 Forward primer: CCTACGGGGNGGCWGCAG, Reverse primer: GACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC) with the silva 138 database (Quast et al, Yilmaz et al., Glöckner et al.) and assigned taxonomy using representative sequences of the OTU table. Unassigned OTUs at the Kingdom level, or assigned as chloroplasts, mitochondria and Archaea were excluded from analysis. We imported the OTU table, taxonomy table and the extended metadata into R version 4.1.0.

Statistics

We used the lme package in R to run a linear mixed effects model to analyze the significance of the respective factors on alpha diversity keeping cage ID as a random factor.

To test the effects of the respective factors on beta diversity we created a bray Curtis distance matrix from the rarefied OTU table using 100 iterations with the vegan package in R. This matrix together with a confounding factor table (cage ID) was imported into Primer + version 6 to run a PERMANOVA. Due to the use of a confounding factor table the PERMANOVA ran with the SS I.